

TABLE 1—VALUES OF PROTONATION CONSTANTS OF LIGANDS

Ligands	Temp. = 27°		
	log K ₁ ^H	log K ₂ ^H	log B
CHBSA	7.46	5.03	12.49
CHSA	5.75	—	5.75
PTT	10.72	—	10.72

CHBSA has the following structure.

The formation curve of CHBSA extends from 0 to 2 on the \bar{n}_A scale indicating its dissociation as

CHSA has the following structure.

The formation curve of CHSA extends between 0 and 1 on the \bar{n}_A scale indicating its dissociation as

Although the molecule has two dissociable protons, only one value corresponding to log K₁^H could be obtained. It may be that the proton present as CH₂COOH dissociates immediately in the solution and its dissociation constant could not be studied in the present work.

PTT, a yet another analytically important reagent^{7,8} has the structure C₆H₅NH-C-NH-C-C₆H₅.

Its formation curve extends between 0 and 1 on the \bar{n}_A scale indicating its dissociation as

With the exception of PTT, in all other cases the complex titration curve (c) extends beyond the ligand titration curve (b). The metal ligand stability constants were calculated by the analysis of the formation curves obtained by plotting \bar{n} against pL. Various computational methods⁹ were applied to evaluate the stepwise formation constants. The error limits are ± 0.03 for log K₁ and ± 0.05 for log K₂. The mean values of concentration stability constants are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF CONCENTRATION STABILITY CONSTANTS OF COMPLEXES

Ligand	Temp. = 27°			Dy ^{III} system		
	log K ₁	log K ₂	log B	log K ₁	log K ₂	log B
CHBSA	9.08	5.70	14.78	5.56	4.05	9.61
CHSA	—	3.45	—	—	2.85	—

Only one value is obtained in case of CHSA systems. The Ce^{IV}-PTT and Dy^{III}-PTT systems could not be studied as there was a precipitation beyond pH 3.0.

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Anion Exchange Separation of Some Metal Ions in Aqueous-Acetone-Dichloroacetic Acid Media. Part-III

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THE use of aqueous-acetone-carboxylic acid media has been shown for ion exchange separation of cations and successful multicomponent separations on anion exchange column were achieved^{1,2}. In continuation of our previous work in acetic and chloroacetic acid media, we have now examined the ion-exchange behaviour of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Mn^{II}, Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Cu^{II} and Cd^{II} on anion exchange resin in aqueous solutions of dichloroacetic acid (DCA) with varying concentrations from 0.5 to 3.0M at various percentages (0-80%) of acetone. The results, such as distribution coefficients and binary and tertiary mixture separations are reported.

Experimental

All reagents and chemicals were of AR grade (B.D.H., E. Merck). Dowex 21K resin (20-50 mesh, Cl⁻ form) was obtained from Dow Chemical Co., U.S.A. Standard solutions of Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, Zn²⁺, Mn²⁺, Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺, Cu²⁺ and Cd²⁺ were prepared by dissolving their chlorides in distilled water and were standardized titrimetrically³.

The experimental procedure of finding the distribution coefficients and separation of mixtures were as described earlier^{1,2}. The resin (1 g) was equilibrated with the solution of metal ion (50 ml, 0.05M) in aqueous and differed aqueous acetone-DCA media for 24 h. The weight distribution coefficients⁵, K_D were calculated.

Separation of mixtures was carried out by feeding the metal ion mixture (10 ml) on the column of height 20 cm and inner diameter 1 cm. The metal ions were eluted by suitable eluting agents. The effluents were collected in a number of fractions of 10 ml each and were estimated complexometrically³.

Results and Discussion

The distribution coefficients of the metal ions were found at 0, 20, 40, 60, 80 percentages of acetone and at 0.5, 1, 2, 3 M concentrations of DCA. The distribution coefficients of Ni²⁺, Mn²⁺, Mg²⁺ at 0.5 and 3 M DCA solutions at all percentages of acetone are low, indicating the tendency of these metals to form less stable anionic complexes or not to form such complexes. Cu²⁺ and Ca²⁺ show the slight tendency to form anionic complexes at 3 M DCA. K_D value (≈50) shows approximately equal distribution of metal ion in solution and resin phases. The distribution coefficients of Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺, Co²⁺ and Ca²⁺ at 3 M DCA are greater than those at 0.5 M DCA at the respective acetone percentages. Cu²⁺ shows slight rise in K_D at 80% acetone-3 M DCA indicating increasing tendency of complex formation at higher percentage of acetone and acid as well. In anion exchange studies it is assumed that a single anionic complex is sorbed on the resin along with excess ligand⁴. The K_D values of Zn²⁺, Co²⁺, Cd²⁺ increase with the rise in acetone concentrations which influenced the dielectric constant of media⁵. Acetone does not display the complexing ability in the systems. There is no measurable change in K_D values of Co²⁺ in 0.5 M DCA at all percentages of acetone. In the case of 3 M DCA the distribution coefficients of Co²⁺ is ≈ 80 in zero and 20% acetone. These K_D values increase with the rise in acetone percentage. Co²⁺ forms a blue coloured anionic complex at 80% acetone-3 M DCA, the same stable complex was also observed in 80% acetone-3 M acetic acid¹ and chloroacetic acid². Zn²⁺ and Cd²⁺

show maximum K_D values under the same conditions. The K_D data of the metal ions suggest the following selectivity sequence.

Separations of Co²⁺, Cd²⁺ and Zn²⁺ from Mg²⁺, Mn²⁺, Cu²⁺ and Ca²⁺ were carried out by selective sorption technique. On passing the binary mixture, the anionic complexes of Co²⁺, Cd²⁺ and Zn²⁺ were retained on the column and all other cationic metal ions passed unadsorbed. Co²⁺ was eluted with water, Cd²⁺ with 5% acetone-0.1 M DCA and Zn²⁺ with 20% acetone-0.5 M DCA. The elution of Co²⁺ was easy. Zn²⁺ and Cd²⁺ were taken up very strongly in comparison to Co²⁺. Therefore, in tertiary mixtures Zn²⁺ or Cd²⁺ and Co²⁺ were retained on column in 80% acetone-3 M DCA, while Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺, Mn²⁺, Mg²⁺ and Ca²⁺ were eluted. Co²⁺ was then eluted with 60% acetone-3 M DCA, finally Zn²⁺ and Cd²⁺ were eluted with the above mentioned eluents. The elution of the metal ions started quickly (BTV ≈ 5-10 ml). It was maximum with ≈ 40-50 ml eluent (VEP ≈ 40-50). The separation of each constituent metal ion was carried out with 60 to 90 ml of the eluent (TEV ≈ 60-90) and took 1-1.5 h.

Quantitative separation of synthetic binary and tertiary mixtures were successfully carried out in the present studies. Mg, Cu, Mn, Ca, Ni metal ions were separated from Co, Cd and Zn. The recovery of each constituent metal ion is more than 90%. The elution curves of the separations of the mixtures are distinct and bell shaped. The metal ions do not interfere with each other and are separated one after the other.

By comparing our present results in DCA with those in acetic acid and CA reported earlier^{1,2}, it is found that the distribution coefficients of Co²⁺, Cd²⁺ and Zn²⁺ in 60-80% acetone-3 M DCA are greater than those in 60-80% acetone-3 M acetic acid or CA. These metal ions are thus strongly held by resin and greater separation factor suggests more accurate separation of ions.

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